

**FORMING THE SKILLS OF READING AND CONSCIOUS
UNDERSTANDING OF THE TEXT IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS
BASED ON NEUROPEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE.**

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Annotation: It is about forming the skills of reading and conscious understanding of the text in elementary school students based on neuropedagogical knowledge.

Key words: Neuropedagogical, reading, awareness, complex skills, framework, brain, processes, neuroscience.

The world that is developing day by day imposes on people the need to be constantly aware of everything that is happening around them. The desire to know the world in school-aged children encourages them to understand new information. And this passion and action play an important role in mastering new material in the learning process. One of the most important and complex skills to be formed in this regard is mastering the learning process. We all know that writing and reading have been crucial to education and scientific progress since the dawn of mankind.

Therefore, today's topic is one of the current topics. Primary school serves as the main foundation for the student's education. We see that today there are great changes and innovations in the field of education. That is why it is very important and relevant to work on the text in primary grades. First, we will answer the question of what is the text itself. The explanation of the concept of text can be found in a number of literatures in a similar sense. For example, in the "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" the concept of text is defined as follows. "The text is derived from the Arabic word, shoulder; expression of speech in writing means text and is interpreted as an author's work or document formed in writing" [5.557]. Y. M. Lotman states that "the text should have the signs of expressiveness (expressing a certain idea), limitation (normality in content and expression) and structural integrity".[4.67] Another researcher A.

According to Hajiyeu, the text is the side-by-side letters, speech reflected through writing, a fragment of speech in general; text[6.61].

The main task of elementary school mother tongue and reading classes is to prepare students for educational activities, to form a person who can communicate with others and convey his thoughts to others in an understandable way. In the teaching of mother tongue and reading literacy, the main focus is on the development of these language skills in the student: reading comprehension, listening comprehension, speaking and writing, and grammatical literacy [1. 128.].

Here the question arises: What is reading comprehension? Researcher Tursunova Dildora defines reading comprehension as the ability to perceive and apply in practice the forms of written language required by society and valued by people. The process of understanding the text seems to be the process of actively processing it, actively selecting the important components that make it an internal component of the extended text. There are many other definitions of comprehension: "Comprehension is the process of understanding the internal relationships in the text", "comprehension is the movement towards knowledge, the production of knowledge in the process of receiving the text", etc. Summarizing the variety of definitions, it is clear that the category of understanding is closely related to the understanding of "meaning": meaning is the most important component of the essence of understanding. In the process of mastering the text and analyzing what is read, students understand its content and the importance of leading ideas in it.

Studying is an important process in human life that ensures the acquisition of new knowledge, the preservation of traditions, the development of critical thinking, the formation of moral values, and the spiritual and cognitive transformation of a person. Thus, this skill covers the entire educational process, starting before learning the alphabet. At the beginning of the school year, primary school teachers have a great responsibility, that is, the alphabet period is considered an important period, and it is their task to ensure that their students become competent readers by the end of the first years. Thus, the main pedagogical task in primary schools is to teach students to read

and understand consciously. Neuropedagogical knowledge, which is now considered a new branch of pedagogy, can help us temporarily solve this problem.

According to international pedagogical experiences, comprehensive and in-depth knowledge of children requires taking into account their psychophysiological characteristics as well as their neurological capabilities and aspects. Neuropedagogy is a scientific field that studies the interaction of the brain and education, combining the knowledge of neurobiology, psychology and pedagogy. Scientist J. Bogen conducted research in the field of neuropedagogy, and instead of traditional activities based on the activation of the left hemispheres, he proposed imaginative, emotional education aimed at activating the right hemispheres [2].

At present, systematic scientific research conducted by M. Gazzaniga, E. Kendel, R. Munakata in the field of cognitive neuroscience deserves special attention. According to the above-mentioned scientists, since human thinking is subjective, his emotions help to make better decisions than logical ones. In Uzbekistan, some issues of improving the quality of education through the use of neuropedagogical knowledge (B. Khodjaev) and developing neuropedagogical characteristics of children in the conditions of an innovative educational environment (J. G'ulomov, N. Yunusova, V. Anvarova) have been studied. lib, large-scale scientific research in this field has not been carried out yet [3].

Developing reading and comprehension skills is the focus of every primary school teacher around the world. This skill has many key components. It should be recognized that the development of conscious reading of the text is the basis not only for the perfect study of knowledge in the subject of reading, but for the study of all subjects. For example, if a student encounters difficulty while reading a problem in mathematics, he will certainly not understand it and will not be able to solve the problem.

We can rely on neuropedagogical methods to teach conscious reading of the text. We will cite one method as an example. A text is selected from the textbook by the teacher, and we divide the text into three parts for their conscious understanding. After reading the first part, we tell the students to draw a picture corresponding to this part.

The student imagines how to draw the picture while reading the text and begins to draw it in his mind. We draw the same pictures for the second and third parts. After all the students have finished drawing their pictures, they will have to retell the text based on the picture. This method, on the one hand, encourages the student to work independently on himself, and on the other hand, helps to understand the conscious and deep content of the text.

In conclusion, it is an important and difficult process to focus students' attention on the lesson in primary education. This is a responsible task for the teacher. It is effective to consciously teach the text with different methods, taking into account the age and individual characteristics of students.

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